

Integrated trophic position as a proxy for food-web complexity

1. Supporting text

Data fitting using the Weibull distribution

In Fig. 5c, some data points deviated from the regression curve. Thus, we fitted the data to the Weibull distribution, which is considered a generalized exponential distribution. Its shape parameter $A_{wb} = 1$ corresponds to an exponential distribution. Therefore, we determined how close the data were to an exponential distribution by estimating the shape parameter A_{wb} . We fit the biomass distribution using the following function:

$$f(k)_{wb} = \frac{A_{wb}}{B_{wb}} \left(\frac{k - 1.5}{B_{wb}} \right)^{A_{wb}-1} \exp \left[- \left(\frac{k - 1.5}{B_{wb}} \right)^{A_{wb}} \right]. \quad (S1)$$

Fig. S5 shows that most of the data were distributed around $A_{wb} = 1.2$. In this case, the Weibull distribution can be approximated to an exponential distribution, which supports our assumption that most biomass distributions obey exponential functions.

iTP reconstruction using central difference equation

The iTP values were also reconstructed from a central difference equation (hereafter referred to as iTP_{cd}) using A_{ex} values. In general, the exponential function f meets the following condition:

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$$\frac{df}{dk} = -\frac{1}{A_{ex}}f. \quad (S2)$$

In this case, the difference in biomass between TL m and k is given as follows:

$$\frac{B^{(m)} - B^{(k)}}{m - k} = -\frac{1}{A_{ex}} \frac{[B^{(m)} + B^{(k)}]}{2}. \quad (S3)$$

Using Equations 16 and S3, iTP_{cd} is determined as follows:

$$iTP_{cd} = -\frac{[B^{(m)} + B^{(k)}]}{2(B^{(m)} - B^{(k)})} + 1.5, \quad (S4)$$

where m and k were set at 2 and 3, respectively, to determine whether biomass at low TLs predicts the total iTP value. The deviation between iTP_{cd} and the observed iTP values was assessed using Equation 20. Reconstruction was good enough for $iTP < 2.5$, although the deviation increased as iTP increased (Fig. S8).

2. Supporting table and figures

Table S1. Metadata of food-web models downloaded from EcoBase on 10 September 2021.

Figure S1. Distribution of biomass fractions (biomass at trophic level k , $B^{(k)}$, divided by total biomass, B_T , on a log scale) across unfolded trophic levels ($2 \leq k \leq 100$). Color is same as Fig. 2.

Figure S2. Plot for $D_H + (D_V - D_R)$ [horizontal diversity + (vertical diversity–range diversity)], which was computed after food network unfolding (FNU, Equations 4–6) and Shannon diversity index H' , which was computed before FNU (Equation 7). Black line indicates 1:1.

Figure S3. Plot for the integrated trophic position (iTP) calculated before FNU (Food-Web iTP) and after FNU (Food-Chain iTP) (Equation 3). Black line indicates 1:1.

Figure S4. Biomass spectra obtained from TP data without FNU in cases where (a) all species and their own biomass are regarded as nodes and (b) species belonging to a certain TP range are grouped and their biomass was summed. Color is same as Fig. 2.

Figure S5. Shape parameter (A_{wb}) for the Weibull function fitted to the biomass distributions across trophic levels in each of the 158 food webs.

Figure S6. Correlation matrix for the three D indices, i.e., horizontal diversity (D_H), range diversity (D_R), and vertical diversity (D_V) and Shannon's diversity index H' . For comparison, each subplot is arranged in the same manner as that of Fig. 5 of Kato et al. (2018).

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Figure S7. Plots for (a) the exponential fitting parameter A_{ex} reconstructed using the central difference equation vs. the observed integrated trophic position (iTP)–1.5 and (b) the standardized residual χ of the central difference equation (χ_{cd}) vs. the iTP. Red line indicates 1:1.

Figure S8. Correlation between the partial integrated trophic position (iTP) calculated from biomass and trophic position (TP) of species with $2 \leq \text{TP} \leq 3$ and the iTP_{cd} calculated from the central difference equation using the unfolded biomass assigned to trophic level (TL) = 2 and TL = 3.

Figure S9. Top predator trophic position (TP) (food chain length: FCL) vs. integrated trophic position (iTP). Regression line ($y = 1.10x + 1.64$) and its 95% confidence bounds are also shown.

Figure S10. Food chain length (FCL) vs. the three D indices, i.e., (a) horizontal diversity (D_{H}), (b) range diversity (D_{R}), and (c) and vertical diversity (D_{V}), and (d) Shannon's diversity index H' .

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Figure S1

iTP and food-web complexity

Figure S2

iTP and food-web complexity

Figure S3

Figure S4

iTP and food-web complexity

Figure S5

iTP and food-web complexity

Figure S6

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Figure S7

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Figure S8

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Figure S9

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Figure S10

3. References for the EcoBase dataset

The original data sources, such as articles and reports, listed in EcoBase are as follows.

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